

Synthetic methanol for shipping decarbonisation

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Deliverable D1.2

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PU	Public – fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

CHANGE CONTROL

DOCUMENT HISTORY

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is the first data management plan (DMP) of the POSEIDON project. It describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated and is mandatory for each Horizon Europe project. The report will be updated regularly throughout the project. The document follows the structure of the official DMP template from the EU Commission and provides information about 6 main aspects of DMP:

- Data summary – [Chapter 2](#),
- General rules to ensure and provide FAIR data – [Chapter 3](#),
- Specific data management rules applicable to other research outputs – [Chapter 4](#),
- Allocation of resources – [Chapter 5](#),
- Data security and ethics – [Chapter 6](#),
- Safeguarding of IP rights – [Chapter 7](#).

AUTHORS' NOTE

Some paragraphs contained in this document are taken and adapted from previous deliverables submitted by partner Steinbeis in the frame of other H2020 and Horizon Europe project such as D7.2 – Data Management Plan from project MOST-H2- novel metal organic framework adsorbents for efficient storage of hydrogen (GA number 101058547) and D7.1 – Data Management Plan for Long COVID Syndrome project (GA number 101057553).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
CC 0	Creative Commons Zero License
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FP	Framework Programm
IP	Intellectual Protection
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
LCC	Life Cycle Costing

S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Analysis
SO	Specific Objective
TEA	Techno Economic Analysis
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is the first version of the data management plan (DMP) of project POSEIDON. It defines the framework for data acquisition, organisation and sharing within the project and beyond. The DMP describes the types of data used or generated, the standards to be used to ensure interoperability, the methods to be followed to store data in a secured and findable manner. It explains how data access and reusability are regulated and how compliance with the IP management plan and open science practices outlined in the Grant Agreement and CDE plan (see D7.1) is ensured.

This document is based on a collaborative work coordinated by partner Steinbeis involving all project partners. A workshop took place on October 11th 2023 focusing on the definition of the e-methanol value chain. This workshop helped in identifying the essential bricks of the value chain and data that can be provided by the project partners to perform the project tasks. Further complementary information was provided by work package leaders who gave feedback regarding the data to be generated or used within their WP and data practices to be followed. This DMP report is primarily based on assumptions made by project partners, as many technical tasks have not yet been started. An update of the DMP plan will be provided in yearly project activity deliverables (D1.4-6) and technical reports to be submitted to the EU commission at the end of each project year and of each project period respectively. It is highly likely that some of the elements presented in this document will be amended or completed when updating the DMP.

The structure of this document is based on the official template of the DMP for Horizon Europe. Questions from the template have been inserted and highlighted with blue color in certain chapters of this document from chapter 3 onwards.

2 DATA SUMMARY

The POSEIDON project aims at implementing new value chains for the use of synthetic methanol as fuel for ships to support decarbonisation of the shipping sector. This will be achieved by connecting local stakeholders through the formation of so-called communities of practice, by building a performant power-to-e-methanol prototype plant based on a novel concept. The plant will be tested in relevant operational environment and the produced fuel will be used in 2-stroke and 4-stroke engine to assess its compatibility. To quantify the value created under different scenarios, detailed technical, economic, environmental, and social studies will be performed. A replication tool to evaluate the feasibility of deployment of e-methanol in EU ports will be developed, so that external EU stakeholders can make use of the results of POSEIDON.

There are several data to be produced during the project that belong to the following main categories:

- Raw data generated by the demonstration and testing of the e-methanol synthesis technology and engines,
- Database in the form of digital libraries on components and technologies mainly based on historical data found in the literature or provided by partners necessary for the development of digital tools and needed for the detailed assessment studies,
- Technical diagrams and engineering documents and associated digital twins that will support the building of the e-methanol synthesis technology and its future integration in the test platform for further qualification,
- Software-and related documentation and source code that will serve to perform engineering studies, LCA studies and techno-economic evaluations,
- Project deliverables and written reports containing the main results of the work drafted by POSEIDON partners. These reports draw on the processing and analysis of data and information. Some are labelled sensitive and others as public,
- Dissemination materials such as project videos, flyers, scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals, conference papers, articles in industrial journals that are intended to promote the project, its activities, and results.

2.1 TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA THAT THE PROJECT WILL GENERATE OR REUSE

The table below presents the different types of data to be generated or re-used during the project. A non-exhaustive list of data-based results of the project is provided in [Annex](#). For each data type, the formats of data to be used is specified.

Table 1: Main data and associated formats to be generated or reused within POSEIDON

Dataset / research output	Data formats
Raw data gained from the testing activities of the prototype for methanol synthesis, 2-stroke and 4-stroke engines and from laboratory activities related to the testing of membrane gas absorption for CO ₂ capture	Data from prototype testing: xlsx, csv Data from engine testing: xlsx
Databases on components and technologies used for digital tools and detailed technic-economic assessments and market studies	Database on technologies and components: xlsx, csv Database on industrial CO ₂ emitters (CEREN, Enerdata): xlsx, csv EU emissions database (EUTL, IREP): csv Database on EU vessels traffic (Seaweb, Sea intelligence): csv, json, xml
Technical diagrams and engineering files needed for the construction for the methanol synthesis prototype	Process Flow Diagramm: pdf Piping and Instrumentation Diagramm (PID): pdf 3D drawing: step, stp

Software code of the digital tools (modelling and replication tools, digital twins of the prototype and of the full renewable fuel testing platform) and related documentation	LCA tool: csv LCC tool: csv LCA and S-LCA tool: csv Digital twin: apw Value chain modelling tool: json, java, python, csv Tool documentation: docx
Project deliverables and written reports	Written report: pdf, docx, xlsx Video: avi, flv, mov, mp4, wmv
Digital dissemination materials used to promote the project	Written report: pdf, docx, pptx Video: avi, flv, mov, mp4, wmv Picture: jpeg, raw, psd, ai, tiff

2.2 ORIGIN/PROVENANCE OF THE DATA

As indicated in the chapter introduction, the data generated within the project will have different origins:

1. Some of the data will be generated through laboratory activities, test campaigns, modelling and detailed socio-economic, environmental and technical assessments. This data will originate from test equipment, modelling tools, as well as TEA and LCA software and tools, respectively,
2. Another large part of data to be generated within the project are databases needed to run the modelling tools for the simulation of scenarios and databases needed to perform market studies and identify suitable locations for fuel production and use. The origin of this data will largely be external to the project and will either be provided directly by the project partners or come from open-source literature or in some cases fee-based databases,
3. A third category of data encompasses more technical and engineering data required for the construction of the e-methanol prototype and associated development of digital twins. This category of data will be produced using standard engineering software and tools,
4. The remaining data are written reports and dissemination materials that will compile project results generated in all POSEIDON work packages by the project partner. This data will present the main project results and be shared with the European Commission and the main target groups via communication and dissemination measures.

2.3 PURPOSE OF DATA GENERATION AND ITS RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

POSEIDON is an innovation action focusing on the demonstration of new technologies and the preparation of the implementation of new value chains in Valencia, Spain and Thessaloniki, Greece and other EU ports. To qualify the innovative technologies built in the project and assess the value

to be created by the new value chains, its will be necessary to do engineering studies and perform test campaigns and detailed economic, environmental, and social studies. POSEIDON is therefore a data-driven research project in which a lot of information is to be gained from the data obtained. The data and information produced will also serve to validate business models needed for the characterisation of key exploitation results and to publish articles in journals to disseminate the main results towards the target groups.

Data generation will be particularly high for the following specific objectives of POSEIDON:

- SO2 – Build and demonstrate innovative, efficient, and sustainable solutions for the “e-methanol as fuel for vessels” value chain,
- SO3 – Evaluate the impacts and evidence the value creation along the e-methanol value chain,
- SO4 – Pave the way for market uptake and future deployment of e-methanol in EU,
- SO5 – Foster the adoption of e-methanol as an alternative fuel for ships through targeted dissemination and communication.

Although the first specific objective SO1 – Connect stakeholders and lay the foundations of a cost-effective and sustainable e-methanol value chain for shipping in two ports, Valencia and Thessaloniki will involve tasks focusing on the development of technical databases for the analysis of complete chains, these activities are considered to be less intensive in terms of data production than tasks from the other objectives, since they will be based mainly on the collection and processing of data from existing sources.

2.4 STAKEHOLDERS OUTSIDE THE PROJECT THAT COULD BENEFIT FROM POSEIDON DATA

POSEIDON follows an open science strategy. Project partners are committed to guaranteeing open access to knowledge and high value research outputs to the EU research community, provided that it does not interfere with the rights of each partner to exploit its own results. This is to be achieved through the proper management and documentation of data, the use of standards data format and data processing tools, the sharing of methods and results within the consortium to avoid methodological biases and ensure soundness of research findings, the presentation of results in a simple, scientific and appealing manner, and finally the dissemination of results towards the main target groups. These actions should facilitate the uptake of results and further use in follow-up research and innovation projects which is expected to lead to the development of new innovative solutions for the decarbonisation of the shipping sector. The target groups expected to benefit from POSEIDON data are presented in the table below.

Table 2: Target groups to benefit from POSEIDON data

TG#	Target group
TG1	Vessel operator
	Ship builders including engine manufacturers

	Fuel suppliers
TG2	E-fuel plant operators (could potentially be stakeholders belonging to TG3 or TG4 such as feedstock providers, utility company or port operators)
TG3	Feedstock providers (chemical companies, lime producers, wastewater treatment plant operators, biogas plant operators)
	Energy utilities and energy companies providing renewable power
TG4	Port operators/authorities and local authorities
	Project developers, engineering offices and system integrators
TG5	EU research and scientific community
TG6	Wider EU e-methanol community including associations, expert and interest groups, similar projects
TG7	Policy makers and standardisation / IP bodies
TG8	General public / civil society

To safeguard the exploitation rights of each partner and comply with the open science strategy, a thorough IP assessment will be carried out in the frame of the exploitation workshops to determine which project results will be considered for 1) unrestricted open science dissemination and 2) enhanced protection measures to safeguard exploitation of results in accordance with the IP and exploitation strategy of each partner (for additional information, see chapter 7).

2.5 EXPECTED SIZE OF DATA TO BE RE-USED OR GENERATED

The size of data to be re-used or generated is difficult to estimate at the time of writing of this report since only a few technical activities are already ongoing. It can be assumed that the size of written reports and presentations will be in the range of 1-5 MB each while video files and engineering files generated with specific software will be bigger in size and amount to several MB or even GB. Depending on the number of data to be collected and processed, the size of the databases to be created and used for the development of digital tools and the conduction of different studies will probably be several hundred MB in size. POSEIDON is a highly data-driven research project, and it can be expected that the size of all data generated by the project will represent several TB by the end of the project.

3 GENERAL RULES TO ENSURE AND PROVIDE FAIR DATA

POSEIDON follows the FAIR principles¹ to guarantee that research data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The measures to be taken are described in the following sections.

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE

Will data be identified with persistent identifier?

Not all data will be identified with a persistent identifier but only data that will be shared in open access such as publications and data shared on open data platform such as Zenodo. A persistent identifier is automatically assigned to data shared in open access when they are uploaded on such platforms. For “internal project data” that will mostly be used within the project to produce intermediate or final results, a so called “document naming convention” will be followed allowing to identify a document quickly and easily. Following rules inspired by the file name conventions of the University of Aberdeen² will be observed:

- Keep file names short,
- Order the elements in a file name in the most appropriate way,
- Avoid unnecessary repetition in file names,
- Avoid obscure abbreviations or acronyms,
- Avoid using invalid characters such as “* ? ! / \ : # % ~ { } “
- Dates should always follow the same format YYYYMMDD,
- For numbers 0-9, always use a minimum of two-digit numbers to ensure correct numerical order,
- The version number of a record should be indicated by the inclusion of “v” followed by the version number (i.e. “v01”, “v02”).

The internal data produced within POSEIDON should contain at least the following information in this sequence: 1. The date of publication or document completion (e.g. “20231221”), 2. the internal file identifier if available (e.g. “D1.1” corresponding to deliverable D1.1), 3. the document name (e.g. “ProjectManagementPlan”), 4. the file version (e.g. “v02”), 5. and the file extension (e.g. “pdf”). When taken together, this leads to the following file name:

“20231221 D1.1 ProjectManagementPlanv02.pdf”.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? Will search keywords be provided in the metadata? Will metadata be catalogued for easy search?

Rich metadata will be provided to allow for quick discovery. As described in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement, metadata of 1. deposited publications and 2. data must be open under a Creative

¹ OpenAIRE project, “Guide for researchers – how to make your data fair”, <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>, last accessed January 2024

² University of Aberdeen, „File Naming Conventions: simple rules save time and effort”, <https://www.abdn.ac.uk/staffnet/documents/policy-zone-information-policies/File%20Naming%20Conventions%20July%202017.pdf>, last accessed November 2023

Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent. It is key that metadata contain detailed information about the shared file.

For publications, metadata must include at least the following:

- author(s),
- title,
- data of publication,
- publication venue,
- Horizon Europe funding (grant project name, acronym and number),
- licensing terms,
- persistent identifiers for the publication.

For deposited data, metadata must consist of at least the following:

- description,
- date of deposit,
- author(s),
- venue and embargo,
- Horizon Europe funding (grant project name, acronym and number),
- licensing terms,
- persistent identifiers for the dataset.

With regard to keywords, partners will be advised to reuse the keywords used when submitting the POSEIDON proposal, such as "e-methanol", "renewable e-fuel for maritime transport", "e-methanol-based value chains", "valorisation of biogenic and industrial CO₂ sources". Depending on the publication or research data submitted, other keywords related to the content of the file may be added.

What general standards will be followed?

As indicated in the previous sections, standards for document naming used in the EU research community will be used for internal project documents while persistent identifier will serve to identify deposited publications and research data. Furthermore, rich metadata containing essential information as set out in Annex 5 of the GA will be provided to allow for easy discovery.

3.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Will all data be made available?

Not all data will be made available. Only the data that are labelled as "open" and that partners do not want to retain confidential for exploitation purposes will be shared on open data platforms. The labelling of data either as "open" or "confidential" will take place when project partners will jointly define and characterise key exploitable results in the framework of the exploitation workshops (for more information on IP management, see chapter 7).

Will data be deposited in a trusted repository? Does the repository ensure that the data will get an identifier?

Open data will be deposited in trusted repository such as Zenodo. The data to be deposited will include public deliverables, open-access peer-reviewed publications and open data generated by

the project. In addition to this platform, some academic partners may use their own platforms to publish results and publications related to POSEIDON in open access. To the extent possible, it will be ensured that data get a unique identifier to ease data search and accessibility.

Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0? Will metadata contain information on how to access the data? Will documentation about any software needed to access the data be included in the metadata?

As indicated in the previous subchapter, metadata will be provided to allow for quick discovery. In compliance with the provisions set out in annex 5 of the Grant Agreement, metadata of deposited publications and data will be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent. If a specific software needs to be used to access and/or process the data, a detailed documentation with clear guidelines will be provided to the users of the data. As described in more depth in the following section, project partners will seek to use to the extent possible open source software to make data as much interoperable as possible.

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will be followed to allow data exchange and re-use across disciplines?

Vocabularies, standards, formats and methods followed will be those commonly used in the research areas covered by the projects, such as energy and alternative fuels as general research topics and the research fields directly linked to the project activities like CO₂ capture and feedstock valorisation, chemical plant development and engineering, life cycle assessment and techno-economic analysis and market studies. In WP5, the life cycle costing approach to be followed is the one defined by Hunkeler et al. (doi: 10.1201/9781420054736). Similarly, the life cycle assessment work will be carried out according to the guidelines defined in ISO 14044. The market studies to be undertaken in WP6 will be based on national and European databases open to all like Eurostat and Enerdata. Furthermore, standardised test methods will be used in WP2 for the work on innovative CO₂ capture technologies, and in WP4 for the testing of the e-methanol synthesis prototype and engines tests. Partners in charge of these activities have a strong experience in data handling and management and will use formats and methodologies commonly used in the respective research field to ensure interoperability of data. Thus, re-use of data across disciplines will be guaranteed.

In case you use uncommon or specific ontologies or vocabularies will you provide mappings to more commonly used ones? Will your data include references to other data from your project or dataset from previous research?

To maximise interoperability of data, specific vocabularies will generally be avoided and, if they are used because, for example, of a poor fit with standard vocabularies, detailed information will be provided to make data as comprehensive as possible. Furthermore, if used in POSEIDON, datasets from similar and earlier projects will be clearly distinguished and referenced for interoperability purposes, and the work carried out by other organisations and researchers will be duly acknowledged.

3.4 INCREASE DATA REUSE

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use?

The consortium intends to ensure reusability of data by providing sufficient information on methodology and assumptions required to support data interpretation and reuse. Clear information on data license will be published so that future users of data know what kinds of data re-use are permitted.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?

As stated previously, not all data will be made freely available since it will be important not only to promote open research but also to properly manage foreground IP to safeguard the exploitation of key exploitable results. Thus, a thorough analysis of the exploitation potential of a result will be conducted before the result is published and available in the public domain. In the case where partners have approved the release of data, every effort will be made to ensure that data published in the public domain meets the FAIR conditions and can be easily used and re-used under the appropriate license. Once scientific publications and data will be made accessible through Zenodo, they will be freely available indefinitely.

Will your data be licensed under standard reuse licenses in lines with the obligations set out in the GA?

Metadata and deposited data will use standard reuse licenses such as Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent in line with the FAIR principles. As shown by the table below, this type of license allows for the maximum flexibility for a third party willing to reuse the data.

Table 3: Types of licenses (adapted from EPFL, <https://www.epfl.ch/education/educational-initiatives/cede/training-and-support/selecting-the-appropriate-licence/>, last accessed January 2024)

	Copy and publish	Attribution required	Commercial use	Modify and adapt	Change license	Comments/ Explanations
CC 0 (No rights reserved)	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes	Users can distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, with no conditions
CC BY (Attribution)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Users must give appropriate credit

						to the original work
CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		If users transform, or build upon the material, the new contributions must be distributed under the same license as the original
CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Users cannot recombine or edit the content, only share it as it is
CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Users cannot use the works in any commercial context

Will the data be usable by third parties in particular after the end of the project? Describe the main data quality processes to be followed?

All data that will be deposited on open data platforms such as Zenodo will be available indefinitely and thus be usable by third parties. The data quality lifecycle management of POSEIDON will consist of the following four main steps: 1. Metric identification and definition, 2. Quality assessment, 3. Data repairing and cleaning, 4. Data storage and archiving.

4 SPECIFIC DATA MANAGEMENT RULES APPLICABLE TO OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS (SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS, DIGITAL MODELS)

4.1 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

In line with the overall CDE strategy of POSEIDON (see deliverable D7.1), open access to peer-reviewed scientific publication will be guaranteed by:

- uploading data, results, and associated publications in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and providing immediate open access under license CC BY or equivalent,
- informing users of the repository of any research outputs, tools, or instruments necessary to validate the conclusions of the scientific publications,
- encouraging preregistration and preprints within POSEIDON to ensure rapid dissemination of results and get feedback from the research community.

This is expected to increase the uptake of results and may lead further collaborations and follow-up studies.

4.2 DIGITAL MODELS

Although is highly uncertain that the IT models developed within POSEIDON like the modelling tool of the e-methanol value chain and digital twins of the e-methanol plant prototype will be openly accessible due to their high scientific and business exploitation values, the development of IT models will follow high quality standards so that interoperability and reusability criteria are met in the event of protective measures being lifted in the future. The modelling tool to be developed by partner EIFER will consist of several separate models representative of a single value chain steps which all interconnected together will allow to simulate and compare various value chain scenarios. This approach should also be beneficial for model reusability since single models corresponding to specific value chain steps can be more easily repurposed this way.

5 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What will be the costs of making data and research outputs FAIR and how will these costs be covered?

The costs for making POSEIDON research data fair are detailed in the grant agreement. Specific budget for open access dissemination was allocated to most of the project partners so that they can covers costs incurred when publishing in open access. Partner Steinbeis in charge of the CDE activities has additional budget to be used for the payment of domain name and web hosting for the POSEIDON official project webpage that will allow to highlight the main project research outputs and make public deliverable accessible to a large audience.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data management in POSEIDON will be coordinated by partner Steinbeis and this task will be supported by all work package leaders including partners EIFER, ICODOS, EDF, CERTH, FVP. Steinbeis will oversee data management at project level while the work package leaders will coordinate data management actions at work package level. All project partners will support data management activities and comply with the FAIR principles described in this document.

To track data and other materials produced within POSEIDON, a monitoring table will be used. This table will be completed as soon as new data become available. This table will present detailed information on new/reused data and corresponding formats. Following information will be collected:

Table 4: Main information to be collected in the DMP monitoring table

Data description

File ID	Short description	Meta data	Related WP	Origin data	of	Partners involved in data generation
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Data format				
Format	File size	Related WP	Link	Dissemination status

How will long term preservation be ensured? What would be the necessary resources needed to accomplish this?

To ensure long term preservation of research data, the data management process initiated within the project will be continued after project end: the project account created on the ZENODO platform will remain online and be updated and populated with new data, for example if data relating to POSEIDON tasks becomes only available after the end of the project.

Data management is also a process that will go on at partner level. It is expected that the results of POSEIDON will lead to new Horizon Europe or FP10 follow-up research and innovation projects and that the FAIR data produced within POSEIDON will be still accessible on EU open data platforms, either under the POSEIDON account or under new accounts. If the latter is the case, information will be provided to users of these platforms so that they can easily make the link between POSEIDON’s data and all new related research projects relying on or reusing this data.

The necessary resources for data preservation are estimated to be low and require little time investment (i.e. yearly maintenance of open data accounts). This is why costs are also considered to be low, and if significant costs were to become necessary, the project partners would try to have them covered by follow up projects. To ensure that long term preservation is ensured, roles and commitments must be clearly defined. Responsibilities will be outlined in the last update of the DMP of POSEIDON data to be drafted towards the end of the project.

6 DATA SECURITY AND ETHICS

6.1 DATA SECURITY

What provisions will be in place for data security including data recovery, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data?

All partners are responsible for the security of data that they generate and use in the frame of the project activities. At partner level, most data will be stored digitally on servers that are protected from unauthorized access and feature backup services that allow to restore lost or damaged data. The transfer of large sensitive data such as results from test campaigns or findings from studies will only

be permitted if a secured data transfer solution approved by internal regulations of partners involved in the exchange is used. For the storage and exchange of all other types of data and documents, partners will use the MS Teams and Sharepoint solution put in place and managed by coordinator EIFER. All partners have access to this web-based collaborative platform that is compliant with data security standards and allows to store and restore data of different types. It contains almost all data, documents and reports produced within POSEIDON and will be populated throughout the project.

6.2 ETHICS

Are there or could there be any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

There are no serious ethics or legal issues that could affect data sharing. POSEIDON is a data-driven research project that will focus on the handling of technical data. Only a few personal data will be necessary for project management tasks and the communication with members of the advisory board and members of the communities of practice in Valencia and Thessaloniki. High attention will be paid to this data by following European procedures and guidelines (see below), by storing them in safe and secure ways, by restricting the access to this data to only a few project members, and by putting mailing lists in place. The latter will help in reducing the risk of misuse of email addresses through data minimisation.

Will other European/national/sectorial procedures for data management be followed?

The data management framework that will be followed within POSEIDON is in line with EU key procedures for data management and the current regulations on data protection such as the General Data Protection Regulation that became effective in EU on 25 May 2018. If there is any doubt as to the procedure to follow, advice will be sought from the data protection officers from partners EIFER and Steinbeis.

7 SAFEGUARDING OF IP RIGHTS

The successful exploitation of the research results of POSEIDON is key to achieving the long-term impacts of the project such as the deployment of new infrastructure for the refueling of alternative fuel like e-methanol in European ports. Therefore, it is important to keep a good balance between open science practices to comply with the open science strategy of the project and confidentiality of IP produced within the project to safeguard the exploitation rights of partners. A careful screening of foreground IP will be undertaken in the framework of the exploitation workshops and implications of disclosing confidential IP will be thoroughly assessed before disseminating project results. The methodology to be applied to appropriately balance open science and IP protection interests is depicted in the picture below.

Figure 1: Sequence of activities between IP management/exploitation activities and dissemination activities in POSEIDON

8 CONCLUSION

This deliverable presents the first version of the DMP of project POSEIDON. It outlines the main data to be generated or reused and the procedures to be followed to ensure FAIR data. The development of this plan was coordinated by partner Steinbeis. This document is based on the collaborative work of the consortium: a first workshop on value chain mapping held in October 2023 helped in identifying data to be provided by project partners to perform project tasks. Furthermore, WP leaders specified the type and formats of data to be generated and reused for their specific WP. It should be noted that this document is based on many assumptions, as most of the data-generating technical activities have not yet begun. The DMP will be regularly updated throughout the project and updates will be provided to the European Commission when drafting and submitting technical reports.

9 ANNEX

9.1 NON-EXHAUSTIVE LIST OF DATA-BASED RESULTS TO BE PRODUCED/USED IN POSEIDON AND RELATION WITH PROJECT TASKS

Task	Related data
2.2	Data on several alternative e-fuels to feed the study on decarbonisation of the maritime sector
2.4-2.5	Library on components and technologies including CO ₂ capture, hydrogen production, engines for WP5 studies and value chain simulation tool
2.5	Scenarios of complete value chains
3.1	Process Flow Diagramm (PFD) and Piping and Instrumentation Diagramm (PID), 3D drawings
3.2	Historical data used to develop and validate a dynamic simulation model/digital twin of the ICODOS plant (Aspen, Aspen plus, Aveva)
3.4	Process control and automation design
4.4	Results from different tests of ICODOS prototype at EDF lab (first campaigns under normal conditions and second one under stress conditions), data will be used to calibrate digital twins
4.5	Results from engines tests and engine simulation models
5.1	Data on upstream and downstream costs for TEA and LCC including data on carbon prices and costs of alternative decarbonisation options
5.2	Data needed to perform a well-to-wank environmental assessment considering end of life stage of e-methanol
5.3	Data required for social assessment based on literature review and questionnaire
5.4	Database to run the value chain modelling tool
5.1-5.4	Results from TEA, LCC, LCA, S-LCA studies by using new developed methodologies and modelling tool
6.1	Database on industrial sites, renewable plants and industrial processes suitable for e-methanol production
6.2	Data on EU vessel traffics and data on shipping companies for investigation of e-methanol use
6.3	Results from business model characterisation

6.5	Database (data on feedstock, vessels, and various EU' power mix) needed to run replication tool
7.2	Communication materials including flyers, newsletters, video
7.3	Dissemination materials including scientific articles, conference papers, video of workshops and events
7.4	Detailed information on key exploitable results including exploitation, ownership, protection and access claims
7.5	Project guidebook presenting main project results